

E-ISSN: 2746-9107

P-ISSN: 3047-4248

JOURNAL OF SOCIETY INNOVATION AND DEVELOPMENT

The multidisciplinary journal of society for development

JSID

www.journal.institutre.org

Supported by

Translation Equivalence in the Song "Mine" by Petra Sihombing with the Indonesian Version

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Abstract

This study aims to find out the equivalence of the meaning of the translation of the songs "Mine" and "Milikku" by Petra Sihombing from English to Indonesian, both of which were written by the songwriters themselves. The approach used is a qualitative descriptive approach. The problem faced is the difference in the number of syllables or syllables needed to convey the message in the sentence as a whole with the availability or limitation of syllables in the melody of the song. The method used refers to the translation method according to Mona Baker, which emphasizes the level of equivalence of the meaning of the target language (TL). Two songs that have been translated by the songwriters themselves are used with two different song versions. The results of the study show that the song cannot be translated perfectly into the target language, but the songwriter can translate it as close as possible to the equivalent meaning into the target language by looking at the equivalence of words and meanings, the structure of the song, and the impact of the song on listeners in the target language. so that the message in the song can be conveyed properly.

Keyword: Translation; Equivalence; Mona Baker; Song; Mine

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Received 28 January 2024; Received in revised form 02 May 2024; Accepted 10 May 2024; Available online 18 May 2024

<https://doi.org/>

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This paper is in collaboration with Universitas Negeri Yogyakarta

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INTRODUCTION

Translating in the context of music, especially songs, presents a unique challenge for translators. "Lyrics or song verses can be considered as poetry and vice versa, encompassing not only literary genres but also expressions that are advertising, proverbs, slogans, prayers, and pop song lyrics" (Luxemburg & Henri, 1989). In other words, translating song lyrics requires a high level of language skills and a deep understanding of the equivalence of meaning between the source and target. Songs have strong emotional power and can connect people from various backgrounds. Therefore, precise equivalence of meaning is crucial for the message and emotions in the song to be accurately conveyed to listeners with different backgrounds.

The song "Mine" by Petra Sihombing, with Petra Sihombing himself as the songwriter (Sihombing, Mine, 2013), is an English-language song originating from Indonesia. Due to its popularity in Indonesia, a few months later, Petra Sihombing released an Indonesian version of the song titled "Milikku" (Sihombing, Milikku, 2014). Both versions of the song were written and released by Petra Sihombing himself, making them original and/or official works of Petra Sihombing.

In relation to translation analysis in songs, the strategies used by translators can vary. Some common strategies often employed include: preserving the original meaning of the lyrics, adapting the meaning to the target culture, maintaining flow and rhythm, and capturing the emotions conveyed in the lyrics. Each strategy has its own strengths and challenges, depending on the translation goals at hand. The objective of this research is to analyze the equivalence of meaning in the translation strategies used within the song. Through this analysis, we can understand how translators express the meaning and nuances contained in the original lyrics to listeners from different backgrounds (Mus, 2024; Zainuddin, 2019; Bahri, 2019; Nugroho, 2020; Misbah, 2029).

Because translation is a form of communication, the primary task in translation practice is to establish equivalence between the original text and the target language (Yinhua, 2011). In other words, every translation involves some form of equivalence between the source text and the target text; without a certain degree of equivalence or specific aspects, a translation cannot be considered a translation of the original text. "A common problem often encountered is the loss of meaning and emotion in songs that have been translated from their original language" (Johanis & Pendit, 2022). Therefore, it is necessary to analyze the equivalence of meaning in song translations.

The theory of translation equivalence proposed by Catford states that 'translation equivalence as an empirical phenomenon, discovered by comparing the ST and the TT; and, on the other hand, the conditions underlying, or justifying, translation equivalence' (Catford, 1965) can be concluded that equivalence of meaning is an empirical phenomenon that can be found by comparing the source text with the target text. According to Vinay and Dalbernet, 'The method of creating equivalence is also often applied to idioms' (Vinay & Darbelnet, 1995); in other words, equivalence of meaning can also be applied to idioms. With this concept, there is another explanation related to the concept of equivalence that equivalence indicates that ST and TT have a 'similarity' 'equivalence is intended to show that the source text (ST) and the target text (TT) have some kind of 'similarity' (Panou, 2013; (Cristina, 2024; Munidar, 2024; Rahmadan, 2024; Johan, 2024).

Mona Baker's explanation in her book about levels of translation equivalence 'begins at the simplest level and grows in complexity by expanding its focus' (Baker, 2018). The levels of equivalence referred to by Mona Baker in her book are as follows:

1. 'Equivalence at the word level', initially adopting a naive building block approach and exploring the meanings of individual words and expressions.
2. 'Equivalence above the word level', the scope of reference is slightly expanded by looking at combinations of words and phrases: what happens when words begin to combine with other words to form conventional or semi-conventional language sequences.
3. 'Grammatical equivalence', related to grammatical categories such as number and gender.
4. 'Textual equivalence: thematic and structural', the order of words in composing a message at the text level.
5. 'Textual equivalence: cohesion', the grammatical and lexical relationships linking various parts of the text.
6. 'Pragmatic equivalence', looking at how texts are used in communicative situations involving variables such as author, reader, and cultural context.
7. 'Semiotic equivalence', moving beyond verbal expression to explore the interaction between verbal and visual elements in various genres such as comics, films, children's literature, and concrete poetry.
8. 'Beyond equivalence: ethics and morality', intended to encourage students to reflect on the broader implications of their decisions and the impact of their mediation on others.

Based on the explanations provided, the formulated issues are as follows:

1. Is the translation equivalence of meaning in the song "Mine" by Petra Sihombing good and correct?
2. What is the level of translation equivalence of meaning used by the translator for the song "Mine" by Petra Sihombing?

METHOD

This research is a qualitative descriptive study. Conclusions are drawn after the data analysis is collected. The research analysis highlights the linguistic aspects of both versions of the song by Petra Sihombing, "Mine" and "Milikku". Subsequently, the data is analyzed descriptively to address the research issues. The data in this study consists of two song lyrics, namely "Mine" and "Milikku". These two song lyrics are then compared by the author to determine the equivalence of their translation meanings. Both songs were chosen for analysis not only because they have been used to support worship, but also to examine the equivalence of words and meanings, song structure, and the impact of the song on listeners in the target language.

FINDING AND DISCUSSION

Finding

Before delving into the explanation of the results and discussion, the author will provide the lyrics of two versions of Petra Sihombing's song 'Mine' and 'Milikku', as follows:

Girl your heart, girl your face
is so different from them others

Wajahmu, hatimu
telah lama kudambakan

I say, you're the only one that I'll adore
 'Cause every time you're by my side
 My blood rushes through my veins
 And my geeky face, blushed so silly yeah
 And I want to make you mine

kamu yang sejak dulu aku nantikan
 ketika kau di sampingku
 berdebar rasa di hatiku
 diriku tersipu malu karna dirimu
 ku ingin kau milikku

Oh, baby, I'll take you to the sky
 Forever you and I, you and I, you and I
 And we'll be together 'til we die
 Our love will last forever and forever you'll be
 mine, you'll be mine
 Girl your smile and your charm
 Lingers always on my mind
 I'll say you're the only one that I've waited for
 And I want you to be mine

Oh baby I'll take you to the sky
 Forever you and I, you and I, you and I
 dan kita 'kan slalu bersama
 cintaku selamanya jika kamu milikku milikku
 senyummu candamu
 selalu dapat kubayangkan
 kamu yang sejak dulu aku nantikan
 ku ingin kau milikku

Oh, baby, I'll take you to the sky
 Forever you and I, you and I, you and I
 And we'll be together 'til we die
 Our love will last forever and forever you'll be
 mine, you'll be mine

Oh baby I'll take you to the sky
 Forever you and I, you and I, you and I
 dan kita 'kan slalu bersama
 cintaku selamanya jika kamu milikku
 milikku

And I want you to be mine
 And I want you to be mine

And I want you to be mine
 And I want you to be mine

Oh, baby, I'll take you to the sky
 Forever you and I, you and I, you and I
 And we'll be together 'til we die
 Our love will last forever and forever you'll be
 mine, you'll be mine

Oh baby I'll take you to the sky
 Forever you and I, you and I, you and I
 dan kita 'kan slalu bersama
 cintaku selamanya jika kamu milikku
 milikku

Oh, baby, I'll take you to the sky
 Forever you and I, you and I, you and I
 And we'll be together 'til we die
 Our love will last forever and forever you'll be
 mine, you'll be mine

you and I
 dan kita 'kan slalu bersama
 cintaku selamanya jika kamu milikku
 milikku milikku

In presenting the results, the author aligns the findings as answers to the previously outlined problem statements. Below are the results presented in the form of a table along with brief descriptions explaining the contents of the table.

Table 1. Equivalence

Num	Source Text (ST)	Target Text (TT)	Information
1.	Girl your heart, girl your face	Wajahmu, hatimu	Equivalent

2.	is so different from them others	telah lama ku dambakan	Not Equivalent
3.	I say you're the only one that I'll adore	kamu yang sejak dulu aku nantikan	Not Equivalent
4.	'Cause every time you're by my side	ketika kau di sampingku	Equivalent
5.	My blood rushes through my veins	berdebar rasa di hatiku	Equivalent
6.	And my geeky face blushed so silly yeah	diriku tersipu malu karna dirimu	Equivalent
7.	And I want to make you mine	Ku ingin kau milikku	Equivalent
8.	Oh baby I'll take you to the sky	Oh baby I'll take you to the sky	Not Translated
9.	Forever you and I you and I you and I	Forever you and I you and I you and I	Not Translated
10.	And we'll be together 'til we die	dan kita 'kan slalu bersama	Equivalent
11.	Our love will last forever and forever you'll be mine you'll be mine	cintaku selamanya jika kamu milikku milikku	Equivalent
12.	Girl your smile and your charm	senyummu candamu	Equivalent
13.	Lingers always on my mind	selalu dapat kubayangkan	Equivalent
14.	I'll say you're the only one that I've waited for	kamu yang sejak dulu aku nantikan	Equivalent
15.	And I want you to be mine	ku ingin kau milikku	Equivalent

In Table 1, the equivalence of meaning in the songs 'Mine' and 'Milikku' by Petra Sihombing is good and correct; the intended message in the source text (ST) can be conveyed to the target text (TT) for different listeners. However, there are still some song translations that are not equivalent. Overall, the equivalence of meaning in delivering the message to the listeners is good and correct in both versions of the song.

Table 2. Level of Equivalence

Num	Source Text (ST)	Target Text (TT)	Information
1	Girl your heart, girl your face	Wajahmu, hatimu	Gramatical
2	is so different from them others	telah lama ku dambakan	Not Equivalent
3	I say you're the only one that I'll adore	kamu yang sejak dulu aku nantikan	Not Equivalent
4	'Cause every time you're by my side	ketika kau di sampingku	Gramatical
5	My blood rushes through my veins	berdebar rasa di hatiku	Gramatical

6	And my geeky face blushed so silly yeah	diriku tersipu malu karna dirimu	Gramatical
7	And I want to make you mine	Ku ingin kau milikku	Gramatical
8	Oh baby I'll take you to the sky	Oh baby I'll take you to the sky	Not Translated
9	Forever you and I you and I you and I	Forever you and I you and I you and I	Not Translated
10	And we'll be together 'til we die	dan kita 'kan slalu bersama	Gramatical
11	Our love will last forever and forever you'll be mine you'll be mine	cintaku selamanya jika kamu milikku milikku	Gramatical
12	Girl your smile and your charm	senyummu candamu	Gramatical
13	Lingers always on my mind	selalu dapat kubayangkan	Gramatical
14	I'll say you're the only one that I've waited for	kamu yang sejak dulu aku nantikan	Gramatical
15	And I want you to be mine	ku ingin kau milikku	Gramatical

In Table 2, the level of equivalence in the songs 'Mine' and 'Milikku' by Petra Sihombing, where the lyrics are equivalent, all are at the grammatical equivalence level, as explained by Mona Baker in her book.

Discussion

In the process of comparing the lyrics from the source language (ST) to the target language (TT), it always begins with listening to both songs and reading the lyrics repeatedly until understanding what the songwriter intends to convey, whether word-for-word, line-by-line, verse-by-verse, or overall. The discussion below aims to prove the equivalence in meaning.

First Verse

(1) Girl your heart, girl your face	(1) Wajahmu, hatimu
(2) is so different from them others	(2) telah lama ku dambakan
(3) I say you're the only one that I'll adore	(3) kamu yang sejak dulu aku nantikan
(4) 'Cause every time you're by my side	(4) ketika kau di sampingku
(5) My blood rushes through my veins	(5) berdebar rasa di hatiku
(6) And my geeky face blushed so silly yeah	(6) diriku tersipu malu karna dirimu
(7) And I want to make you mine	(7) ku ingin kau milikku

Looking at the first two lines of both lyrics, the songwriter translates sentence by sentence, with the analysis as follows:

(1) Girl your heart, girl your face	(1) Wajahmu, hatimu
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In sentence (1) in both lyrics, the songwriter translates the source text (ST) by omitting the word 'girl' in the target text (TT), with the reason of maintaining the same number of syllables in the song, so that in sentence (1), the song can still be sung with the same syllables.

However, despite this, the removal of the word 'girl' in the target text does not change the meaning, so sentence (1) can be considered equivalent in meaning.

(2) is so different from them others

(2) telah lama ku dambakan

In sentence (2) in both lyrics, the songwriter translates the source text (ST) by completely changing the sentence structure into the target text (TT), thus changing the meaning. Upon further examination, the source text (ST) could still be translated while maintaining meaning and syllables, for example: 'berbeda dengan yang lain' with the same number of syllables as in the source text (ST). However, the communicative impression between the songwriter and the target audience (TT) may change. It can be concluded that sentence (2) in both lyrics can be considered not equivalent in meaning.

(3) I say you're the only one that I'll adore

(3) kamu yang sejak dulu aku nantikan

In sentence (3) in both lyrics, the songwriter translates the source text (ST) by completely changing the sentence structure into the target text (TT), thus changing the meaning. Upon further examination, the source text (ST) could still be translated while maintaining the meaning, but it is difficult to maintain the syllables. In the source text (ST), there is 'I'll adore' which has a meaning almost equivalent to 'aku nantikan' in the target text (TT), but overall, it can be concluded that sentence (3) in both lyrics can be considered not equivalent in meaning.

(4) 'Cause every time you're by my side

(4) ketika kau di sampingku

In sentence (4) in both lyrics, the songwriter translates the source text (ST) into the target text (TT) with a sense-for-sense approach, translating freely by changing the sentence structure but still maintaining the meaning. Upon further examination, the source text (ST) could still be translated while maintaining both form and meaning, although it is difficult to maintain the syllables. Therefore, the change in sentence structure in the target text (TT) does not alter the meaning, so sentence (4) can be considered equivalent in meaning.

(5) My blood rushes through my veins

(5) berdebar rasa di hatiku

In sentence (5) in both lyrics, each uses a metaphorical sentence with a meaning that can be considered the same. In other words, the songwriter translates the source text (ST), which is a metaphorical sentence, by similarly using a metaphorical sentence in the target text (TT) that carries the same meaning. Therefore, it can be concluded that sentence (5) in both lyrics has equivalent meaning.

(6) And my geeky face blushed so silly yeah

(6) diriku tersipu malu karna dirimu

In sentence (6) in both lyrics, each uses a metaphorical sentence with a meaning that can be considered the same. In other words, the songwriter translates the source text (ST), which is a metaphorical sentence, by similarly using a metaphorical sentence in the target text (TT) that carries the same meaning. Therefore, it can be concluded that sentence (6) in both lyrics has equivalent meaning.

(7) And I want to make you mine

(7) Ku ingin kau milikku

In sentence (7) in both lyrics, the songwriter translates the source text (ST) by slightly changing the form and structure of the sentence into the translated sentence (TT), with the reason of maintaining the same number of syllables in the song, so that in sentence (7), the song can still be sung with the same syllables. However, despite this, the change in form and structure of the source text (ST) into the target text (TT) does not alter the meaning, so sentence (7) can be considered equivalent in meaning.

Second Verse

(8) Oh baby I'll take you to the sky

(8) Oh baby I'll take you to the sky

(9) Forever you and I you and I you and I

(9) Forever you and I you and I you and I

(10) And we'll be together 'til we die

(10) dan kita 'kan slalu bersama

(11) Our love will last forever and forever
you'll be mine, you'll be mine

(11) cintaku selamanya jika kamu milikku
milikku

Looking at the second lines of both lyrics, the songwriter translates sentence by sentence, with the analysis as follows:

(8) Oh baby I'll take you to the sky

(8) Oh baby I'll take you to the sky

In sentence (8) in both lyrics, the songwriter does not translate the source text (ST) and retains it as is. Therefore, the text in the source language (ST) is used as it is in the target language (TT). This sentence is very iconic, hence the songwriter does not translate it.

(9) Forever you and I you and I you and I

(9) Forever you and I you and I you and I

In sentence (9) in both lyrics, the songwriter does not translate the source text (ST) and retains it as is. Therefore, the text in the source language (ST) is used as it is in the target language (TT). This sentence is very iconic, hence the songwriter does not translate it.

(10) And we'll be together 'til we die

(10) dan kita 'kan slalu bersama

In sentence (10) in both lyrics, the songwriter translates the source text (ST) by removing the phrase 'til we die' in the target text (TT), with the reason of maintaining the same number of syllables in the song, so that in sentence (10), the song can still be sung with the same syllables. However, despite this, the removal of the phrase 'til we die' in the target text (TT) does not change the meaning, so sentence (10) can be considered equivalent in meaning.

(11) Our love will last forever and forever
you'll be mine, you'll be mine

(11) cintaku selamanya jika kamu milikku
milikku

In sentence (11) in both lyrics, the songwriter translates the source text (ST) by slightly changing the form and structure of the sentence into the translated sentence (TT), with the reason of maintaining the same number of syllables in the song, so that in sentence (11), the song can still be sung with the same syllables. However, despite this, the change in form and structure of the source text (ST) into the target text (TT) does not alter the meaning, so sentence (11) can be considered equivalent in meaning.

Third Verse

(12) Girl your smile and your charm

(12) senyummu candamu

(13) Lingers always on my mind I'll say

(13) selalu dapat kubayangkan

(14) You're the only one that I've waited for

(14) kamu yang sejak dulu aku nantikan

(15) And I want you to be mine

(15) ku ingin kau milikku

Looking at the second lines of both lyrics, the songwriter translates sentence by sentence, with the following analysis:

(12) Girl your smile and your charm

(12) senyummu candamu

In sentence (12) in both lyrics, the songwriter translates the source text (ST) by removing the word 'girl' in the target text (TT), with the reason of maintaining the same number of syllables in the song, so that in sentence (12), the song can still be sung with the same syllables. However, despite this, the removal of the word 'girl' in the target text (TT) does not change the meaning, so sentence (12) can be considered equivalent in meaning.

(13) Lingers always on my mind I'll say

(13) selalu dapat kubayangkan

In sentence (13) in both lyrics, the lyrics in the source text (ST) use a metaphorical sentence, whereas the text in the target text (TT) is not a metaphorical sentence; however, both sentences have more or less the same meaning. In other words, the songwriter translates the metaphorical sentence in the source text (ST) by using a non-metaphorical sentence in the target text (TT) with the same meaning. Therefore, it can be concluded that sentence (13) in both lyrics has equivalent meaning.

(14) You're the only one that I've waited for

(14) kamu yang sejak dulu aku nantikan

In sentence (14) in both lyrics, the songwriter translates the source text (ST) by slightly changing the form and structure of the sentence into the translated sentence (TT), with the reason of maintaining the same number of syllables in the song, so that in sentence (14), the song can still be sung with the same syllables. However, despite this, the change in form and structure of the source text (ST) into the target text (TT) does not alter the meaning, so sentence (14) can be considered equivalent in meaning. The source text (ST) in sentence (14) is slightly different from the source text (ST) in sentence (6), but the target text (TT) in sentence (14) is the same as the target text (TT) in sentence (6).

(15) And I want you to be mine

(15) ku ingin kau milikku

In sentence (15) in both lyrics, the songwriter translates the source text (ST) by slightly changing the form and structure of the sentence into the translated sentence (TT), with the reason of maintaining the same number of syllables in the song, so that in sentence (15), the song can still be sung with the same syllables. However, despite this, the change in form and structure of the source text (ST) into the target text (TT) does not alter the meaning, so sentence (15) can be considered equivalent in meaning. The source text (ST) in sentence (15) is slightly different from the source text (ST) in sentence (7), but the target text (TT) in sentence (15) is the same as the target text (TT) in sentence (7).

Furthermore, the song lyrics consist mainly of repetition, so the subsequent verses are not analyzed as they contain repeated lyrics. However, there are slight differences in the following lyrics upon closer examination. This is due to some changes in the musical composition in the Indonesian version of the song, resulting in a slightly different approach to the repetition of lyrics at the end compared to the original English version of the song.

CONCLUSION

The songs "Mine" and "Milikku" by Petra Sihombing are one song with two different versions written directly by the songwriter. In terms of translation equivalence of the song's meaning, the version "Milikku" is overall good and correct, and the message in the "Mine" version can be effectively conveyed to Indonesian listeners through the "Milikku" version. However, there are still some meanings that are not equivalent in the translation sentence by sentence in both versions of the song. When considering the overall meaning, both versions of the song approach near-perfect equivalence, beyond form and structure equivalence. It is important to note that the level of meaning equivalence in both versions of the song is at the grammatical equivalence level as theorized by Mona Baker.

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